

**BUMBY'S TECHNIQUE AND A RESULT OF LIOUVILLE
ON A QUADRATIC FORM**

Jesse Ira Deutsch

Mathematics Department, University of Botswana, Private Bag 0022, Gaborone, Botswana
deutschj_1729@yahoo.com

Received: 2/15/07, Accepted: 4/19/07, Published: 8/1/08

Abstract

A new proof of a Theorem of Liouville on representations by a quadratic form is given. A modification of a technique of Bumby using quaternions is utilized in the demonstration.

1. Introduction

The study of quaternion rings can yield insights into questions related to certain quadratic forms. In previous work the author proved the formula for the number of representations of a positive integer by a universal quadratic form emulating Hurwitz's classic demonstration (see [7] and [2]). This formula was first discovered by Liouville (see [3, p. 227]), and states that for the quadratic form $f = x^2 + y^2 + 2z^2 + 2w^2$ the number of representations of a positive integer $2^a m$ with m odd is

$$4\sigma(m) \text{ for } a = 0, \quad 8\sigma(m) \text{ for } a = 1, \quad 24\sigma(m) \text{ for } a \geq 2. \quad (1.1)$$

Here $\sigma(m)$ is the standard sum of divisors function. The above demonstrations developed the arithmetic number theory of certain related quaternion orders to the point that one could count the number of quaternions of requisite type and given norm. This yielded the number of representations of a positive integer by the corresponding quadratic form in addition to the formula for the number of such representations with extra parity conditions. See [7] and [2] for details.

Here we develop a more direct proof of the representation formula emulating recent work of Bumby [1] for the sum of four squares. Instead of using the arithmetic number theory of the relevant quaternion order, we need only consider a restricted class of ideals. By counting

generators of such ideals, we derive the formula for \mathbf{i} -primitive representations of a positive integer by the quadratic form. An \mathbf{i} -primitive representation is one in which two related algebraic integers are relatively prime in a quadratic number ring. We then build up to the formula for arbitrary representations.

We use the notations of [2, 3] in describing quaternions and related algebraic structures. The above form f is also known as $(1, 1, 2, 2)$. The corresponding quaternion order is

$$H_{1,2,2} = \mathbb{Z} \left[1, \mathbf{i}, \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \mathbf{i} + \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} \right), \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \mathbf{i} + \sqrt{2}\mathbf{k} \right) \right]. \tag{1.2}$$

The notation $\mathbb{Z}[\dots]$ means the \mathbb{Z} module generated by the enclosed elements. We use the notation $\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \mathbf{v}_3, \mathbf{v}_4$ for the generators indicated in equation (1.2) in sequence. The order $H_{1,2,2}$ is known to be norm Euclidean and a maximal order. There are 24 units, left and right greatest common divisors and other properties. One particularly useful property is that any element with even norm has $1 + \mathbf{i}$ as both a left factor and as a right factor. All ideals of $H_{1,2,2}$ under consideration are left ideals, i.e. closed under multiplication on the right. Also relevant to the problem is the submodule with rational integer coefficient quaternions,

$$H_{1,2,2}^0 = \mathbb{Z} \left[1, \mathbf{i}, \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}, \sqrt{2}\mathbf{k} \right]. \tag{1.3}$$

It should be noted that every element of $H_{1,2,2}$ has an associate in $H_{1,2,2}^0$. See [2, 3] for demonstrations and references.

2. \mathbf{i} -primitive Representations

While Bumby considers \mathbf{j} -primitive representations of an integer n as a sum of four squares as the fundamental building block, some modifications have to be made to accommodate the situation for the form $(1, 1, 2, 2)$. We define $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ as the ring of integers of the splitting field of the equation $x^2 + 2 = 0$ over \mathbb{Q} , where \mathbf{j} is specified as the imaginary element. A typical element of $H_{1,2,2}$ can be written as

$$a + b\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} + (c + d\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})\mathbf{i}, \quad a, b, c, d \in \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{Z}. \tag{2.1}$$

Set $\alpha = a + b\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ and $\beta = c + d\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$. Then a typical element is of the form $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ with $\alpha, \beta \in \frac{1}{2}O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Similar to [1] we have the formulas

$$\beta\mathbf{i} = \mathbf{i}\bar{\beta}, \quad N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = \alpha\bar{\alpha} + \beta\bar{\beta} = a^2 + 2b^2 + c^2 + 2d^2, \tag{2.2}$$

where the overline represents conjugation. Note that $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$ precisely when α and β are in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. We can now make the following definition.

Definition 1. Let $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}$ as above be an element of $H_{1,2,2}^0$. Then $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}$ is \mathbf{i} -primitive iff $\gcd(\alpha, \beta)$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ is a unit.

In this situation we generally say that the greatest common divisor of α and β is one. For simplicity we will often ignore unit factors in the description of greatest common divisors. Analogous to the four squares case we have the further definitions below.

Definition 2. The number of representations of a rational integer n by the form $(1, 1, 2, 2)$ is denoted by $s_4(n)$. The number of \mathbf{i} -primitive representations is $s_4^0(n)$. The number of representations of n by the quadratic form $x^2 + 2y^2$ is $s_2(n)$.

The formula for $s_2(n)$ for positive n is known, namely

$$s_2(n) = 2 \left\{ \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d \equiv 1 \pmod{8}}} 1 + \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d \equiv 3 \pmod{8}}} 1 - \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d \equiv 5 \pmod{8}}} 1 - \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d \equiv 7 \pmod{8}}} 1 \right\} \tag{2.3}$$

(see [5, p. 72, (31.12)]). It can be shown directly and without much difficulty that $\frac{1}{2}s_2(n)$ is a multiplicative function.

As an analogue of Proposition 3 in [1], we have the following.

Theorem 3.

$$2s_4(n) = \sum_{d|e=n} s_2(d) s_4^0(e) \tag{2.4}$$

Proof. The proof is the same as in [1] except for the fact that there are two units in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ instead of four as in the Gaussian integers. The fact that $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ is a unique factorization domain is necessary for the demonstration. \square

3. Principal Ideals in $H_{1,2,2}$

Elementary considerations and the commutativity of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ yield the following.

Lemma 4. Let I be a one sided ideal of $H_{1,2,2}$. Then $I \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ is a two sided ideal of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$.

The nature of the ideal of intersection is a useful key to later results. For the rest of this section, let I be the left ideal generated by some $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}$ in $H_{1,2,2}$.

Lemma 5. *Suppose $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}$ is \mathbf{i} -primitive in $H_{1,2,2}$. Let I be as above. Then $I \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (\lambda)$ a principal ideal in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Let $m = N(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i})$. Then up to units $m = \lambda, \lambda\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ or 2λ .*

Proof. Since $m = N(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}) = (\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}) \cdot \overline{(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i})} \in I$ and $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ it follows that $m \in I \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. This implies $m \in (\lambda)$, so $\lambda \mid m$ in the ring $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Since $\lambda \in I$ there exists $\gamma + \delta \mathbf{i}$ in $H_{1,2,2}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda &= (\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i})(\gamma + \delta \mathbf{i}) \\ &= \alpha\gamma - \beta\bar{\delta} + (\beta\bar{\gamma} + \alpha\delta)\mathbf{i}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

Because $\lambda \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ we have $\beta\bar{\gamma} + \alpha\delta = 0$. If $\alpha = 0$ then from $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) = 1$ we find that β is a unit in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. In this case $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i} = \beta \mathbf{i}$ so $\beta \mathbf{i} \cdot \mathbf{i} = -\beta \in I$. Thus $-\beta \in I \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (\lambda)$ which forces λ to be a unit of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. But $m = N(\beta \mathbf{j}) = 1$ so $m = \lambda$ up to units of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$.

The other case occurs when $\alpha \neq 0$. Then $\delta = -\beta\bar{\gamma}/\alpha$. Since $2\gamma, 2\delta \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ we may write $2\delta = -\beta(2\bar{\gamma})/\alpha$ from which it follows that $\alpha \mid 2\bar{\gamma}$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$.

Going back to the equation for λ

$$\lambda = \alpha\gamma - \beta\bar{\delta} = \gamma \frac{\alpha\bar{\alpha} + \beta\bar{\beta}}{\bar{\alpha}} = \frac{\gamma m}{\bar{\alpha}}. \tag{3.2}$$

Thus $2\lambda = m \cdot (2\gamma/\bar{\alpha})$ so it follows that $m \mid 2\lambda$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$.

Together we have $\lambda \mid m \mid 2\lambda$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Since this quadratic ring is a unique factorization domain where 2 ramifies, we have $2 = -1 \cdot (\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})^2$. The only possibilities up to units for m are $\lambda, \lambda\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$, or 2λ . \square

We call the above result the Lemma on \mathbf{i} -primitive principal ideals.

Lemma 6. *Under the hypotheses of the Lemma on \mathbf{i} -primitive principal ideals, if m is odd then $\lambda = m$ up to units.*

Proof. Since in all cases we have $\lambda \mid m \mid 2\lambda$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$, the fact that m is odd forces $\lambda = m$ up to units. \square

Lemma 7. *Under the hypotheses of the Lemma on \mathbf{i} -primitive principal ideals, m cannot be divisible by 8.*

Proof. Suppose $8 \mid m$ where $m = N(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i})$ and $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}$ is \mathbf{i} -primitive. By Corollary 4 of [2] it follows that $2(1 + \mathbf{i})$ divides $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Thus for some $a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i} = 2(1 + \mathbf{i}) \left(a + b\mathbf{i} + c \frac{1}{2}(1 + \mathbf{i} + \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) + d \frac{1}{2}(1 + \mathbf{i} + \sqrt{2}\mathbf{k}) \right) \tag{3.3}$$

which yields

$$\alpha = 2a - 2b + (c - d)\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}, \quad \beta = 2(a + b + c + d) - (c + d)\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}. \quad (3.4)$$

Thus $\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ divides the greatest common divisor of α and β in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$, a contradiction. \square

We recall the notation $p^k \parallel m$ means that p^k is the highest power of the prime p that divides the integer m .

Lemma 8. *Under the hypotheses of the Lemma on \mathbf{i} -primitive principal ideals, $2 \parallel m$ implies $m = \lambda\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ up to units. If $4 \parallel m$ then $m = 2\lambda$ up to units.*

Proof. Suppose $2 \parallel m$, then $m = 2m_0$ where m_0 is odd. Since $2 \mid m$ by Corollary 4 of [2], $1 + \mathbf{i} \mid \alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Thus there exists $\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}$ such that $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} = (1 + \mathbf{i}) \cdot (\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i})$. This forces $N(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i}) = m_0$. Clearly $m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Also $m = N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ so

$$\begin{aligned} m &= N(1 + \mathbf{i})N(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i}) \\ &= (1 - \mathbf{i})(1 + \mathbf{i})(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i})\overline{(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i})} \\ &= (1 - \mathbf{i})(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})\overline{(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i})} \\ \implies (1 + \mathbf{i})m &= 2(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})\overline{(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i})} \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

by multiplying $(1 + \mathbf{i})$ on both sides. It follows that $(1 + \mathbf{i})m_0$ equals $(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})\overline{(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i})}$ which is an element of the ideal I by definition. Now

$$\mathbf{v}_3 - \mathbf{v}_4 = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}(\mathbf{j} - \mathbf{k}) = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}(1 - \mathbf{i})\mathbf{j} \quad (3.6)$$

so multiplying on the right, the following is also an element of I .

$$(1 + \mathbf{i})m_0 \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}(1 - \mathbf{i})\mathbf{j} = m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}. \quad (3.7)$$

Hence $m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} \in I \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (\lambda)$.

If m_0 were an element of (λ) then as $(\lambda) \in I$ it follows that $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ divides m_0 in $H_{1,2,2}$. Thus $1 + \mathbf{i} \mid m_0$ so $2(1 + \mathbf{i}) \mid m$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Taking norms, this implies $8 \mid m^2$ in \mathbb{Z} , a contradiction. Hence $m_0 \notin (\lambda)$.

By the Lemma on \mathbf{i} -primitive principal ideals, it follows that up to units $\lambda = 2m_0, m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ or m_0 . From the above argument we have $\lambda \mid m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ but λ does not divide m_0 . The only possibility is that $\lambda = m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ up to units.

Suppose $4 \parallel m$. Then we may write $m = 4m_0$ where m_0 is odd. Clearly $m/2 \in \mathbb{Z} \subset O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Since $4 \mid m$ it follows that $2 \mid (\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Hence there exists $\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}$ such that $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} = 2(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i})$. Taking the norm of this expression, we have

$$m = 2 \cdot 2(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i})\overline{(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i})} \implies \frac{m}{2} = (\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})\overline{(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i})} \tag{3.8}$$

so $m/2 \in I$, and thus in (λ) . By the Lemma on \mathbf{i} -primitive principal ideals, $m = \lambda, \lambda\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ or 2λ up to units. As 2λ divides m in this case, the only possibility is that $m = 2\lambda$ up to units. \square

Lemma 9. *Let $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ be an \mathbf{i} -primitive expression in $H_{1,2,2}$. Then there exists $\eta \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ such that $\eta - \mathbf{i} \in I$.*

Proof. Since $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) = 1$ it follows that there exists $\lambda, \mu \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ such that $\lambda\beta + \mu\alpha = -1$. Consider the element of I

$$(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})(\bar{\lambda} + \mathbf{i}\bar{\mu}) = \alpha\bar{\lambda} - \beta\bar{\mu} - \mathbf{i}. \tag{3.9}$$

We need only set $\eta = \alpha\bar{\lambda} - \beta\bar{\mu}$. \square

Lemma 10. *Let $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ be an \mathbf{i} -primitive expression of norm m . Choose η as computed in the previous Lemma. Then the left ideal $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$ equals I .*

Proof. With η as above, $\eta - \mathbf{i} \in I$. Also $(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})\overline{(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})} = m \in I$ so $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, m) \subseteq I$. In the other direction consider

$$\begin{aligned} (\eta - \mathbf{i})(-\bar{\beta}) - m\bar{\mu} &= -(\alpha\bar{\lambda} - \beta\bar{\mu})\bar{\beta} + \beta\mathbf{i} - (\alpha\bar{\alpha} + \beta\bar{\beta})\bar{\mu} \\ &= -\alpha(\bar{\lambda}\bar{\beta} + \bar{\alpha}\bar{\mu}) + \beta\mathbf{i} \\ &= \alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.10}$$

Therefore $I \subseteq (\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$. \square

Note that under the conditions of the Lemma on \mathbf{i} -primitive principal ideals, as a consequence of the above Lemmas we know that for any $\eta \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ such that $\eta - \mathbf{i} \in I$ we have $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 = (\eta - \mathbf{i})(\bar{\eta} - \mathbf{i}) \in I \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Thus $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \in (m)$ if m is odd, $\left(\frac{m}{\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}}\right)$ if $2 \parallel m$, and $(m/2)$ if $4 \parallel m$.

4. Special Ideals in $H_{1,2,2}$

Bumby [1] considers special ideals of the form $(\eta - \mathbf{j}, m)$ in the Lipschitz quaternions in order to produce the formula for \mathbf{j} -primitive representations. There η is a Gaussian integer which satisfies the equation $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$. We perform the analogous study using ideals of the form $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$ with $\eta \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ and the same modular condition on η . The formula for the number of representations by the form $(1, 1, 2, 2)$ is more complex than that of the sum of four squares. This additional level of complication is reflected in the results of the following sections.

Lemma 11. *Let $\eta \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Then $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ has no solutions if $8 \mid m$.*

Proof. Write $\eta = a + b\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$, $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then we are attempting to solve $a^2 + 2b^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{8}$. It is easy to check that there are no solutions to this equation. \square

Theorem 12. *Let $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ be odd and $\eta \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Suppose $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$. Let J be the left ideal $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$. Then there exists an \mathbf{i} -primitive $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$ such that $J = (\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. Furthermore $J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (m)$ and $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = m$ up to a unit of \mathbb{Z} .*

Proof. We start with the notation and discussion as in [1]. $\eta - \mathbf{i} \in J$ implies $(\eta - \mathbf{i})(\bar{\eta} + \mathbf{i}) = \eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \in J$. There exists $\gamma \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ such that $J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (\gamma)$. Thus $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \in (\gamma)$ so $\gamma \mid \eta\bar{\eta} + 1$. This implies $\gcd(\gamma, \eta) = 1$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Since J is a left ideal, $(\eta - \mathbf{i})\bar{\gamma} \in J$ thus $\eta\bar{\gamma} - \gamma\mathbf{i} \in J$. But $\gamma \in J$ so $\gamma\mathbf{i} \in J$ and we conclude $\eta\bar{\gamma} \in J$. Thus $\eta\bar{\gamma} \in (\gamma)$ and therefore $\gamma \mid \bar{\gamma}$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$.

Consider the prime factorization of γ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Primes of \mathbb{Z} ramify, split or remain inert in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. If a prime p splits, then $p = \rho\bar{\rho}$ for ρ a prime of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. If the number of ρ 's in γ does not equal the number of $\bar{\rho}$'s, then γ cannot divide $\bar{\gamma}$. Thus the nonramified primes in γ multiply out to an element of \mathbb{Z} . As the units of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ are ± 1 , γ must equal a rational integer, or a rational integer times $\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$.

If $\gamma = b\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$, $b \in \mathbb{Z}$ then $m \in (\gamma)$ implies $\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} \mid m$. Since m is odd, this is a contradiction. Hence $\gamma = b \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $b \mid m$.

Now $J = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$ so there exists $\theta, \psi \in H_{1,2,2}$ such that $(\eta - \mathbf{i})\theta + m\psi = b$. Multiplying by $\bar{\eta} + \mathbf{i}$ on the left we find

$$(\eta\bar{\eta} + 1)\theta + m(\bar{\eta} + \mathbf{i})\psi = (\bar{\eta} + \mathbf{i})b. \tag{4.1}$$

Hence $m \mid (\bar{\eta} + \mathbf{i})b$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. As m is in the centralizer, the divisibility is on the left and the right. Thus there exists $x, y, z, s \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$(\bar{\eta} + \mathbf{i})b = m(x + y\mathbf{i} + z\mathbf{v}_3 + s\mathbf{v}_4). \tag{4.2}$$

Considering the coefficient of \mathbf{k} on both sides, we find $s = 0$. The coefficient of \mathbf{i} gives the equation $b = my + m \cdot z/2$. Thus $m \cdot z/2 = b - my \in Z$. As m is odd, z must be even. Setting $z = 2z'$ we find $b = my + mz'$. Hence $m \mid b$. Since $b \mid m$ we have $m = \pm b$ and thus $J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (m)$.

Since $H_{1,2,2}$ is a principal ideal domain, there exists $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}$ such that $J = (\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. We may replace $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ with an associate to force $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$. Since $\eta - \mathbf{i} \in J$ there exists $\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}$ such that

$$\eta - \mathbf{i} = (\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})(\gamma + \delta\mathbf{i}). \tag{4.3}$$

Extracting the coefficient of \mathbf{i} we find $-1 = \alpha\delta + \beta\bar{\gamma}$ or multiplying by 2 we have the $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ -integer linear combination $-2 = \alpha(2\delta) + \beta(2\bar{\gamma})$. This implies that the greatest common divisor of α and β divides 2 in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Let τ be this greatest common divisor. Then $\tau \mid \alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ in $H_{1,2,2}$ and hence $\tau \mid m$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Taking norms $N(\tau) \mid N(m)$ in \mathbb{Z} so $N(\tau)$ must be odd. The only divisors of 2 in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ up to units are 1, $\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ and 2. Thus τ is a unit and $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ is \mathbf{i} -primitive.

If $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ were even, then by the Lemmas relating to \mathbf{i} -primitive principal ideals, either 2 or 4 exactly divide $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. If $2 \parallel N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ then

$$(m) = J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = \left(\frac{N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})}{\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}} \right). \tag{4.4}$$

Thus $\pm m\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} = N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ so $2 \mid m\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$, a contradiction as m is odd.

If $4 \parallel N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ then

$$(m) = J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = \left(\frac{N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})}{2} \right). \tag{4.5}$$

Thus $\pm m2 = N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ so $4 \mid 2m$, a contradiction again as m is odd.

We conclude that $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ is odd, so $J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}))$ and $m = N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ up to units of \mathbb{Z} . \square

Theorem 13. *Let $m \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\eta \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ and $4 \parallel m$. Suppose $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$. Let J be the left ideal $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$. Then there exists an $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$ such that $J = (\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. Furthermore $J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (m/2)$ and $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = m$ up to a unit of \mathbb{Z} .*

Proof. Set $m = 4m_0$ so m_0 is odd. Since $H_{1,2,2}$ is a principal ideal domain there exists $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}$ such that $J = (\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. Choosing an appropriate associate and renaming, we obtain $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$.

Set $J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (\gamma)$. Then $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{4m_0}$ implies $4 \mid N(\eta - \mathbf{i})$ which yields $(1 + \mathbf{i})^2 \mid \eta - \mathbf{i}$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Equivalently $2 \mid \eta - \mathbf{i}$. Now $\gamma \in J = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, 4m_0)$ so $2 \mid \gamma$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Hence $2 \mid \gamma$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ as $\gamma/2 \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$.

Set $J_0 = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, m_0)$. Then certainly $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m_0}$ so by the result for odd m 's, $J_0 \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (m_0)$. But $\gamma \in J \subseteq J_0$ so $\gamma \in (m_0)$ and thus $m_0 \mid \gamma$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Together we have $2m_0 \mid \gamma$. In the other direction we have $m = 4m_0 \in J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (\gamma)$. Thus $2m_0 \mid \gamma \mid 4m_0$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$.

Set $\eta = b + c\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$. Then $b^2 + 2c^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{4m_0}$ so $b^2 + 2c^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. From this it follows that b and c must be odd. Let $b = 2b' + 1$, $c = 2c' + 1$ with $b', c' \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then $b^2 + 2c^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{4m_0}$ reduces to

$$b'^2 + b' + 2c'^2 + 2c' + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m_0}. \tag{4.6}$$

We wish to force multiples of $\eta - \mathbf{i}$ to live in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$, that is $(\eta - \mathbf{i})(x + y\mathbf{i} + z\mathbf{v}_3 + s\mathbf{v}_4)$ should have no \mathbf{k} or \mathbf{i} component, while $x, y, z, w \in \mathbb{Z}$. Choosing $z = 2c' + 1$, $s = 0$, $x = -c' - b' - 1$ and $y = -c' - 1$. the above product reduces to

$$-2 \left(2c'^2 + 2c' + b'^2 + b' + 1 \right). \tag{4.7}$$

This is -2 times an odd number as $b'^2 + b'$ is always even. Hence it is an odd multiple of $2m_0$ and also an element of (γ) . Hence γ divides $2m_0$ times an odd quantity, and also divides $4m_0$. Thus γ must equal $2m_0$ up to a unit of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ and we conclude $J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (2m_0) = (m/2)$.

We are left to determine $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. As $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) \in J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ we find that $2m_0 \mid N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. However $J = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, 4m_0)$ and we know 2 divides each of $4m_0$ and $\eta - \mathbf{i}$, so $2 \mid \alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Thus $4 = N(2) \mid N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ in \mathbb{Z} . As m_0 is odd it follows that $4m_0 \mid N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ in \mathbb{Z} .

From $J_0 = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, m_0) = (\alpha_0 + \beta_0\mathbf{i})$. for some $\alpha_0 + \beta_0\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}$ There exists $\theta, \psi \in H_{1,2,2}$ for which

$$\begin{aligned} (\eta - \mathbf{i})\psi + m_0\theta &= \alpha_0 + \beta_0\mathbf{i} \\ \implies (\eta - \mathbf{i})4\psi + m_04\theta &= 4\alpha_0 + 4\beta_0\mathbf{i} \in J. \end{aligned} \tag{4.9}$$

Thus $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \mid 4(\alpha_0 + \beta_0\mathbf{i})$ and taking norms $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) \mid 16m_0$ in \mathbb{Z} . Here we use the results of Theorem 12. If 8 were to divide $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ then $2(1 + \mathbf{i}) \mid \alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ which implies $2(1 + \mathbf{i}) \mid \eta - \mathbf{i}$. Thus $8 \mid N(\eta - \mathbf{i})$ or $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{8}$, a contradiction to previous results. It follows that $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = 4m_0 = m$. \square

Theorem 14. Let $m \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\eta \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ and $2 \parallel m$. Suppose $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$. Let J be the left ideal $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$. Then there exists an $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$ such that $J = (\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. If $2 \parallel \eta\bar{\eta} + 1$ then

$$J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = \left(\frac{m}{\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = m. \tag{4.10}$$

If $4 \mid \eta\bar{\eta} + 1$ then

$$J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (m) \quad \text{and} \quad N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = 2m. \tag{4.11}$$

Proof. Write $m = 2m_0$ with m_0 odd. Let $\eta = b + c\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$, $b, c \in \mathbb{Z}$. Then $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ is precisely the same statement as $b^2 + 2c^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2m_0}$. We have already shown that $b^2 + 2c^2 + 1 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{8}$, thus $2 \mid (b^2 + 2c^2 + 1)$ or $4 \mid (b^2 + 2c^2 + 1)$.

From $b^2 + 2c^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$ we find that b is odd. If c is odd then $b^2 + 2c^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$. If c is even then $b^2 + 2c^2 + 1 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

Set $J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (\gamma)$ for some $\gamma \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. As in previous cases we may choose a generator of J , $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ which is in $H_{1,2,2}^0$.

Consider the case in which $4 \mid \eta\bar{\eta} + 1$. Then c as above must be odd, and $4 \mid N(\eta - \mathbf{i})$ implies $(1 + \mathbf{i})^2 \mid (\eta - \mathbf{i})$ or equivalently $2 \mid \eta - \mathbf{i}$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Since $\gamma \in J = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, 2m_0)$ it follows that $2 \mid \gamma$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Set $J_0 = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, m_0)$. Then $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m_0}$ so by Theorem 12 we find $J_0 \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (m_0)$. Since $\gamma \in J \subseteq J_0$ this implies $\gamma \in (m_0)$ so $m_0 \mid \gamma$. Hence we find $2m_0 \mid \gamma$ in $H_{1,2,2}$.

Since $m = 2m_0 \in J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ it follows that $m \in (\gamma)$ so $\gamma \mid 2m_0$. Hence $\gamma = 2m_0$ up to a unit of $H_{1,2,2}$. Since $2m_0/\gamma \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ the ratio is a unit of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Thus $(\gamma) = (2m_0) = (m)$ as ideals of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$.

From $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) \in (\gamma)$ we see that $2m_0 \mid N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. Since $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in J$ it follows that $2 \mid \alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ in $H_{1,2,2}$ for the same reason $2 \mid \gamma$. Thus $4 \mid N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ in \mathbb{Z} . Together we obtain $4m_0 \mid N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$.

Again consider J_0 as above. By Theorem 12, $J_0 = (\alpha_0 + \beta_0\mathbf{i})$ with $\alpha_0 + \beta_0\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$ and $N(\alpha_0 + \beta_0\mathbf{i}) = m_0$. Also for some $\psi, \theta \in H_{1,2,2}$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_0 + \beta_0\mathbf{i} &= (\eta - \mathbf{i})\psi + m_0\theta \\ \implies 2\alpha_0 + 2\beta_0\mathbf{i} &= (\eta - \mathbf{i})2\psi + 2m_0\theta \end{aligned} \tag{4.12}$$

which implies $2\alpha_0 + 2\beta_0\mathbf{i} \in J = (\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. Thus $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) \mid 4m_0$. Together with the previous result we have $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = 4m_0 = 2m$.

We now consider the case where $2 \mid \eta\bar{\eta} + 1$. In this case $\eta = b + c\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ with b odd and c even. From $2 \mid N(\eta - \mathbf{i})$ we have $(1 + \mathbf{i}) \mid (\eta - \mathbf{i})$. Recall $J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (\gamma)$. Now $\gamma \in J$ so it is a right linear combination of $\eta - \mathbf{i}$ and m . For some $\psi, \theta \in H_{1,2,2}$

$$\gamma = (\eta - \mathbf{i})\psi + m\theta. \tag{4.13}$$

But $(1 + \mathbf{i}) \mid (\eta - \mathbf{i})$ and $(1 + \mathbf{i}) \mid 2 \mid m$ so $(1 + \mathbf{i}) \mid \gamma$. Thus $\gamma = (1 + \mathbf{i}) \lambda$ for some $\lambda \in H_{1,2,2}$. Note that $\mathbf{v}_3 - \mathbf{v}_4 = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}(1 - \mathbf{i})\mathbf{j}$ and $N(\mathbf{v}_3 - \mathbf{v}_4) = 1$ so this is an invertible element of $H_{1,2,2}$. Thus

$$\gamma = (1 + \mathbf{i}) \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}(1 - \mathbf{i})\mathbf{j}(\mathbf{v}_3 - \mathbf{v}_4)^{-1} \lambda = \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}(\mathbf{v}_3 - \mathbf{v}_4)^{-1} \lambda. \tag{4.14}$$

We have $\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} \mid \gamma$ in $H_{1,2,2}$ and hence also in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Considering $J_0 = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, m_0)$ as before we find that $m_0 \mid \gamma$. Hence $m_0 \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} \mid \gamma$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$.

We wish to force multiples of $\eta - \mathbf{i}$ into $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Since $\eta = b + c\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ with b odd and c even, set $b = 2b' + 1$ and $c = 2c'$. Attempting to eliminate \mathbf{k} and \mathbf{i} in the product $(\eta - \mathbf{i})(x + y\mathbf{i} + z\mathbf{v}_3 + s\mathbf{v}_4)$ we may choose the values $z = 2b's + s$, $y = -b's - s$, $x = 2c's - b's - s$. The product becomes

$$(4c'^2 + 2b'^2 + 2b' + 1)s\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}. \tag{4.15}$$

Let $s = 1$ to produce an odd multiple of $\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$. Thus γ divides an odd multiple of $\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Also $m = 2m_0 \in J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (\gamma)$ so $m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} \mid \gamma \mid 2m_0$. As γ cannot equal $2m_0$ times a unit, it must equal $m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ up to a unit of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$.

Recall $J = (\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ for some $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$. We are left with finding $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. Considering J_0 again, we find $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) \mid 4m_0$. Also $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) \mid N(\eta - \mathbf{i})$ so $2 \parallel N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$.

Since $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) \in (\gamma) = (m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ we have $m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} \mid N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. As the norm is a rational integer, it follows $2m_0 \mid N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$. With the above divisibility properties, the only possibility is that $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = 2m_0 = m$. \square

5. Number of \mathbf{i} -primitive Representations

Lemma 15. *Let m be an odd positive integer. The number of \mathbf{i} -primitive representations of m by $(1, 1, 2, 2)$ is 4 times the number of distinct ideals of the form $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$ where η satisfies $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$.*

Proof. By Lemma 10 any \mathbf{i} -primitive representation generates an ideal of the form $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$. From the comments after Lemma 10 we see that $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ when m is odd. Now we need only count the number of distinct ideals of the form $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$ and the number of \mathbf{i} -primitive generators of these ideals.

Given any $\eta \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ such that $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$, Theorem 12 demonstrates the existence of an $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$ that is \mathbf{i} -primitive of norm m and a generator of the ideal $J = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$.

From [2] any odd quaternion is congruent to a unit modulo 2. The choice of possible units is

$$\pm \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1, \mathbf{i}, \mathbf{v}_3, \mathbf{v}_4, -1 + \mathbf{v}_3, -1 + \mathbf{v}_4, -\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{v}_3, -\mathbf{i} + \mathbf{v}_4 \\ -\mathbf{v}_3 + \mathbf{v}_4, -1 - \mathbf{i} + \mathbf{v}_4, -1 - \mathbf{i} + \mathbf{v}_3, \mathbf{v}_3 + \mathbf{v}_4 - \mathbf{i} - 1 \end{array} \right\}, \tag{5.1}$$

though we may ignore the \pm when considering these modulo 2 (see [2]). Since 2 times any element of $H_{1,2,2}$ is in $H_{1,2,2}^0$, we find $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$ is equivalent to $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i} \equiv 1$ or $\mathbf{i} \pmod{2}$, as the other units have denominators.

To count the number of generators of $J = (\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i})$ that are \mathbf{i} -primitive is simple since any such generator is a unit times $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}$ and this product being \mathbf{i} -primitive must be an element of $H_{1,2,2}^0$. Thus it is congruent to 1 or \mathbf{i} modulo 2. Thus we wish to find units x such that $x \cdot \{1 \text{ or } \mathbf{i}\} \equiv 1 \text{ or } \mathbf{i} \pmod{2}$. The possible values for x are $\{\pm 1, \pm \mathbf{i}\}$. Since $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}$ is \mathbf{i} -primitive, $(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}) \mathbf{i} = -\beta + \alpha \mathbf{i}$ is also \mathbf{i} -primitive, and the same hold when multiplying by ± 1 or $-\mathbf{i}$. Thus we have 4 \mathbf{i} -primitive generators and hence 4 \mathbf{i} -primitive representations of m by $(1, 1, 2, 2)$ per ideal of the form listed in the Lemma. \square

Lemma 16. *Let m be an odd positive integer. The number of distinct ideals of the form $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$ where $\eta \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ satisfies $\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ is equal to the number of solutions of the equation $x^2 + 2y^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$.*

Proof. Set $\eta = a + b\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$, $\eta' = a' + b'\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$, $J = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, m)$, and $J' = (\eta' - \mathbf{i}, m)$. Then

$$\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \equiv \eta' \bar{\eta}' + 1 \pmod{m} \tag{5.2}$$

or equivalently

$$a^2 + 2b^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \equiv a'^2 + 2b'^2 + 1 \pmod{m}. \tag{5.3}$$

If $a \equiv a'$, $b \equiv b' \pmod{m}$ then $\eta \equiv \eta' \pmod{m}$ so $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, m) = (\eta' - \mathbf{i}, m)$ and $J = J'$.

In the other direction suppose $J = J'$. Then $\eta - \mathbf{i} - (\eta' - \mathbf{i}) = \eta - \eta' \in J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. By Theorem 12 this intersection is just the ideal (m) , so $\eta \equiv \eta' \pmod{m}$. Consequently $a \equiv a' \pmod{m}$ and $b\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} \equiv b'\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j} \pmod{m}$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Multiply the latter equation by $\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ on both sides to find $2(b' - b) \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$. As m is odd it follows that $b \equiv b' \pmod{m}$. Thus we have a one-to-one correspondence between ideals of the requisite form and the number of mod m solutions to $x^2 + 2y^2 + 1 \equiv 0$. \square

The next corollary follows immediately.

Corollary 17. *Let m be an odd positive integer. The number of \mathbf{i} -primitive representations of m by $(1, 1, 2, 2)$ is 4 times the number of solutions to $x^2 + 2y^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$.*

Definition 18. The number of distinct solutions modulo m of $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ with $\eta \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ and $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ is denoted $D(m)$.

Setting $\eta = x + y\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ it is clear that $D(m)$ is the number of distinct modulo m solutions to $x^2 + 2y^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$.

Lemma 19. Let m be an odd rational integer. Then $D(2m) = 2D(m)$ and $D(4m) = 4D(m)$.

Proof. Let η satisfy $\eta\bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$. The residue classes of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})/(2)$ can be chosen as $\{0, \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}, 1, 1 + \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}\}$. The only elements of this set that satisfy the equation $\gamma\bar{\gamma} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$ are 1 and $1 + \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$. Using the Chinese Remainder Theorem we may solve the system

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &\equiv \eta \pmod{m} \\ \gamma &\equiv \{1 \text{ or } 1 + \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}\} \pmod{2} \end{aligned} \tag{5.4}$$

to yield two solutions modulo $2m$. Any such γ satisfies $\gamma\bar{\gamma} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ and $\pmod{2}$, and hence modulo $2m$. Hence each solution γ modulo m corresponds to two solutions to the equation modulo $2m$.

In the other direction, any γ such that $\gamma\bar{\gamma} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2m}$ is also a solution modulo m and 2. Hence it must come from the construction by the Chinese Remainder Theorem above, and consequently $D(2m) = 2D(m)$.

Similar reasoning yields the relation for $D(4m)$ once we note that there are four incongruent solutions of $\gamma\bar{\gamma} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, namely $\{1 + \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}, 1 + 3\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}, 3 + \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}, 3 + 3\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}\}$. \square

Lemma 20. Let $8 \mid m, m \in \mathbb{Z}$. There are no \mathbf{i} -primitive representations of m by the form $(1, 1, 2, 2)$.

Proof. Suppose such a representation exists. Then $m = N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = \alpha\bar{\alpha} + \beta\bar{\beta}$ where $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) = 1$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. We may set $\alpha = a + b\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}, \beta = c + d\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$. Thus

$$a^2 + 2b^2 + c^2 + 2d^2 \equiv 0 \pmod{8}. \tag{5.5}$$

This forces $a \equiv c \pmod{2}$. If a and c are even then $\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ divides each of $a + b\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ and $c + d\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ so $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) \neq 1$. Thus a and c must be odd. But $a^2 \equiv 1 \equiv c^2 \pmod{8}$ and equation (5.4) reduces to $b^2 + d^2 \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, a contradiction. \square

It follows that any even m with \mathbf{i} -primitive representations either $2 \parallel m$ or $4 \parallel m$. We let m_0 be the odd part of any such even m .

Lemma 21. *Let $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $2 \parallel m$. The number of \mathbf{i} -primitive representations of m by $(1, 1, 2, 2)$ is twice the number of distinct solutions of $x^2 + 2y^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$.*

Proof. By Lemmas 9 and 10 every \mathbf{i} -primitive representation generates an ideal of the form $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, 2m_0)$. By the comments following Lemma 10

$$\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \in \left(\frac{m}{\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}} \right) = (m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}). \tag{5.6}$$

Since $\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \in \mathbb{Z}$ it follows that $\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2m_0}$. We need only count the number of \mathbf{i} -primitive generators with norm $2m_0$ of distinct ideals J of the form $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, 2m_0)$ satisfying the condition $\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2m_0}$.

By Theorem 14, any such ideal has a generator $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$. If $2 \parallel \eta \bar{\eta} + 1$ then $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = 2m_0$ while if $4 \parallel \eta \bar{\eta} + 1$ then $N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = 4m_0$. Thus we must restrict our considerations to the case where $2 \parallel \eta \bar{\eta} + 1$. The gcd of α and β may not necessarily be 1, but since $\eta - \mathbf{i} \in J = (\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$ by the argument following equation (4.3) we have $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) \mid 2$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Up to units this gcd can only be 1, $\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ or 2.

If $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) = 2$ then $2 \mid \alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ which implies $4 \mid N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}) = 2m_0$. This is a contradiction.

Suppose $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) = \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$. Then $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} = \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}(\alpha' + \beta'\mathbf{i})$ where $\gcd(\alpha', \beta') = 1$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Thus $\alpha' + \beta'\mathbf{i}$ is \mathbf{i} -primitive of norm m_0 . Further, for each such \mathbf{i} -primitive representation of m_0 we can produce a generator of an ideal of norm $2m_0$ via multiplication by $\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$. Such an ideal corresponds to the case above where the generator has norm $2m_0$, i.e., the case where $2 \parallel \eta \bar{\eta} + 1$. Thus from the total count of generator of ideals of this form we must subtract the number of \mathbf{i} -primitive representations of m_0 , i.e., 4 times the number of solutions to $x^2 + 2y^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m_0}$.

Let J be an ideal of the above type and restrictions with generator $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$. Then $(1 + \mathbf{i}) \mid \alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Considering $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i}$ modulo 2 we see that $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \equiv 0$ or $1 + \mathbf{i}$ as $1 + \mathbf{v}_3 + \mathbf{v}_4, \mathbf{i} + \mathbf{v}_3 + \mathbf{v}_4 \notin H_{1,2,2}^0$. This follows from the list of residues modulo 2 (see [2, Lemma 5]) and the fact that as twice any element of $H_{1,2,2}$ is in $H_{1,2,2}^0$. If $\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i} \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$ then $4 \mid N(\alpha + \beta\mathbf{i})$, a contradiction. By computation, the only units μ of $H_{1,2,2}$ that yield integer coefficients on multiplication by $1 + \mathbf{i}$ are $\mu \in \pm \left\{ 1, \mathbf{i}, \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}(\mathbf{k} - \mathbf{j}), \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}(\mathbf{k} + \mathbf{j}) \right\}$. Thus eight generators of any of the restricted ideals under consideration have integer coefficients.

We now need the number of distinct ideals of the restricted form, that is $J = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, 2m_0)$, $\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2m_0}$ and $2 \parallel \eta \bar{\eta} + 1$. Suppose η, η' satisfy these conditions and set J as above, $J' = (\eta' - \mathbf{i}, 2m_0)$. Then

$$J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = J' \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) \tag{5.7}$$

as $2 \mid \eta \bar{\eta} + 1$ and $2 \mid \eta' \bar{\eta}' + 1$. Thus if $\eta - \eta' \in (m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})$ then $\eta - \eta' \in J \cap J'$ so $\eta - \mathbf{i} - (\eta' - \mathbf{i}) \in J \cap J'$. It follows that $\eta - \mathbf{i} \in J'$, so $J \subseteq J'$. Similarly we find $\eta' - \mathbf{i} \in J$, so $J' \subseteq J$ and conclude $J = J'$.

In the other direction, if $J = J'$ then $\eta - \mathbf{i} - (\eta' - \mathbf{i}) \in J \cap O(\sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})$, which gives $\eta - \eta' \in (m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})$. So the number of distinct ideals equals the number of distinct η modulo $m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j}$ that satisfy $\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2m_0}$ with $2 \mid \eta \bar{\eta} + 1$. We wish to relate this number to $D(2m_0)$.

Consider the natural mapping of $O(\sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})/(2m_0)$ onto $O(\sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})/(m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})$ where $\gamma + (2m_0)$ maps to $\gamma + (m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})$. This mapping is of index 2 (from the ratio of ideal norms). Thus given some $\eta \in O(\sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})/(m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})$ it corresponds to η and $\eta + m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j}$ in $O(\sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})/(2m_0)$. Calculating

$$(\eta + m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j}) \overline{(\eta + m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})} \equiv \eta \bar{\eta} + (-\eta + \bar{\eta}) m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j} + 2m_0^2 \pmod{4m_0}. \tag{5.8}$$

Set $\eta = a + b \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j}$ then $-\eta + \bar{\eta} = -2b \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j}$. Substituting into the above we find

$$(\eta + m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j}) \overline{(\eta + m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j})} \equiv \eta \bar{\eta} + 2m_0^2 \pmod{4m_0}. \tag{5.9}$$

The left side above is thus congruent to $\eta \bar{\eta} \equiv -1 \pmod{2m_0}$. It is also congruent to $\eta \bar{\eta} + 2 \pmod{4}$. Thus both η and $\eta + m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j}$ satisfy the equation $\gamma \bar{\gamma} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2m_0}$, but one of these satisfies $\gamma \bar{\gamma} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$, and the other is a solution of $\gamma \bar{\gamma} + 1 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$. This follows as $\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$. Thus 2 exactly divides only one of $\gamma \bar{\gamma} + 1$ for $\gamma = \eta$ and $\gamma = \eta + m_0 \sqrt{2} \mathbf{j}$.

Therefore the number of distinct ideals with the requisite properties is $\frac{1}{2} D(2m_0)$. Since there are 8 generators of correct type per ideal, the number of \mathbf{i} -primitive representations is

$$8 \cdot \frac{1}{2} D(2m_0) - 4D(m_0) = 4D(2m_0) - 4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} D(2m_0) = 2D(2m_0), \tag{5.10}$$

the desired conclusion. \square

Lemma 22. *Let $m \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $4 \mid m$. The number of \mathbf{i} -primitive representations of m by $(1, 1, 2, 2)$ is 4 times the number of distinct solutions of $x^2 + 2y^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$.*

Proof. The proof is similar to that of the preceding Lemma.

By Lemmas 9 and 10 every \mathbf{i} -primitive representation generates an ideal of the form $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, 4m_0)$. By the comments following Lemma 10

$$\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \in \left(\frac{m}{2}\right) = (2m_0). \tag{5.11}$$

We need only count the number of \mathbf{i} -primitive generators with norm $4m_0$ of distinct ideals J of the form $(\eta - \mathbf{i}, 4m_0)$ satisfying the condition $\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2m_0}$.

Let $J = (\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i})$ be such an ideal and suppose $2 \nmid \eta \bar{\eta} + 1$. Then as $N(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}) \mid N(\eta - \mathbf{i})$, the highest power of 2 in $N(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i})$ is 2^1 . Thus $N(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i})$ cannot equal $4m_0$ and we may ignore all such η . Hence we need only consider \mathbf{i} -primitive generators of distinct ideals of the form $J = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, 4m_0)$ such that $\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{4m_0}$. By Theorem 13, $J = (\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i})$ with $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i} \in H_{1,2,2}^0$ and $N(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}) = m = 4m_0$.

From $4 \mid N(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i})$ it follows that $2 \mid \alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}$ in $H_{1,2,2}$. Thus $(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i})\mu \in H_{1,2,2}^0$ for any unit μ , so each ideal has 24 generators with rational integer coefficients.

The greatest common divisor of α and β may not necessarily be 1, but as in the previous Lemma we see that $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) \mid 2$. Up to units, $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) = 1, \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$ or 2 in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$.

Suppose $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) = 2$. Then $\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i} = 2(\alpha' + \beta' \mathbf{i})$ where $\gcd(\alpha', \beta') = 1$ in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. Also $N(\alpha + \beta \mathbf{i}) = m_0$. This process is reversible, so we must subtract the number of \mathbf{i} -primitive representations of m_0 from the total, namely $4D(m_0)$.

Suppose $\gcd(\alpha, \beta) = \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}$. Similar reasoning to the above shows that we must subtract the number of \mathbf{i} -primitive representations of $2m_0$ from the total, namely $2D(2m_0)$.

We now need the number of distinct ideals of the restricted form, that is $J = (\eta - \mathbf{i}, 4m_0)$, $\eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2m_0}$ and $4 \nmid \eta \bar{\eta} + 1$. Suppose η, η' satisfy these conditions and set J as above, $J' = (\eta' - \mathbf{i}, 4m_0)$. Then Theorem 13 yields

$$J \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}) = (2m_0) = J' \cap O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}). \tag{5.12}$$

By reasoning similar to the previous Lemma, the number of distinct ideals of the proper type is equal to the number of distinct η modulo $2m_0$ such that $N(\eta) + 1 = \eta \bar{\eta} + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{4m_0}$.

Consider the natural mapping of $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})/(4m_0)$ onto $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})/(2m_0)$. Taking ideal norms, this surjection is of index 4. Each η modulo $2m_0$ corresponds modulo $4m_0$ to

$$\eta, \quad \eta + 2m_0, \quad \eta + 2m_0(1 + \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}), \quad \eta + 2m_0\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}. \tag{5.13}$$

Note that $\{0, 1, 1 + \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}, \sqrt{2}\mathbf{j}\}$ form a complete residue system modulo 2 in $O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$. For any $\kappa \in O(\sqrt{2}\mathbf{j})$ a simple calculation shows that $N(\eta + 2m_0\kappa)$ simplifies to $\eta \bar{\eta}$ modulo $4m_0$. Hence each of the numbers in (5.13) corresponds to a distinct solution counted in $D(4m_0)$. Thus the number of distinct ideals is 1/4 the number of solutions in $D(4m_0)$. Since there are 24 integer generators per ideal, the total number of \mathbf{i} -primitive representations is

$$\frac{1}{4} \cdot 24D(4m_0) - 2D(2m_0) - 4D(m_0) \tag{5.14}$$

which reduces to $4D(4m_0)$ by Lemma 19. \square

6. Count of Solutions

To find the formula for the number of representations by the quadratic form $(1, 1, 2, 2)$ we must count the number of solutions to a certain congruence equation, show a related function is multiplicative, and evaluate the latter function at prime powers. The demonstrations follow Bumby though the particular application is somewhat more complicated (see [1]).

Lemma 23. *The number of solutions of the congruence $x^2 + 2y^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{p^k}$ for prime p is*

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} 1 & \text{all } p, k = 0 \\ 2 & p = 2, k = 1 \\ 4 & p = 2, k = 2 \\ 0 & p = 2, k > 2 \\ (p - 1)p^{k-1} & p \equiv 1, 3 \pmod{8} \\ (p + 1)p^{k-1} & p \equiv 5, 7 \pmod{8}. \end{array} \right. \tag{6.1}$$

Proof. The proof is analogous to the demonstration of Proposition 5 in [1]. The cases of 1, 2, 4, and 8 can be checked by hand. For the case of odd p to the first power, we consider the norm as a mapping

$$N : (\mathbb{F}_p[x]/(x^2 + 2))^\star \longrightarrow \mathbb{F}_p^\star. \tag{6.2}$$

If -2 is not a quadratic residue of p , the number of invertible elements in the ring $\mathbb{F}_p[x]/(x^2 + 2)$ is $p^2 - 1$ as everything but 0 is invertible. Since the norm is onto \mathbb{F}_p^\star , the number of elements of norm -1 is $(p^2 - 1)/\#(\mathbb{F}_p^\star)$ or $(p^2 - 1)/(p - 1) = p + 1$.

If -2 is a quadratic residue of p then let $\alpha^2 \equiv -2 \pmod{p}$. The elements of $\mathbb{F}_p[x]/(x^2 + 2)$ that are not invertible are

$$0, \lambda(x - \alpha), \lambda(x + \alpha) \quad \lambda = 1, \dots, p - 1. \tag{6.3}$$

Thus there are $2p - 1$ noninvertible elements, so $\#(\mathbb{F}_p[x]/(x^2 + 2))^\star = p^2 - 2p + 1$. The number of elements of norm -1 is therefore $(p^2 - 2p + 1)/(p - 1) = p - 1$.

We recall that -2 is a quadratic residue of odd primes p only for those $p \equiv 1$ or $3 \pmod{8}$. To obtain the formula for the number of solutions in the case of p^k one may either use Hensel’s Lemma or show directly that each solution modulo p^k generates p solutions modulo p^{k+1} (see [1]). \square

Lemma 24. $\frac{1}{4} s_4^0(n)$ is a multiplicative function.

Proof. By a standard argument with the Chinese Remainder Theorem, the number of solutions of $x^2 + 2y^2 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$, namely $D(n)$, is multiplicative. That is, $\gcd(mn) = 1$ implies

$D(mn) = D(m)D(n)$. We know

$$s_4^0(n) = \begin{cases} 2D(n) & \text{if } 2 \parallel n \\ 4D(n) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \tag{6.4}$$

Thus $s_4^0(n)/4$ is multiplicative for all values of n except where $2 \parallel n$. Suppose 2 exactly divides one of n or m . With no loss of generality let $2 \parallel m$, so $m = 2m_0$ where m_0 and n are odd. From $D(2m_0)D(n) = D(2m_0n)$ we obtain $\frac{1}{2}s_4^0(2m_0) \cdot \frac{1}{4}s_4^0(n) = \frac{1}{2}s_4^0(2m_0n)$. Divide by 1/2 to get

$$\frac{1}{4}s_4^0(2m_0) \cdot \frac{1}{4}s_4^0(n) = \frac{1}{4}s_4^0(2m_0n) \tag{6.5}$$

and the Lemma follows. \square

From Theorem 3 we have

$$2s_4(n) = \sum_{d|e=n} s_2(d)s_4^0(e) \tag{6.6}$$

where n, d, e are positive integers. Note that if we divide this equation by 8 we find

$$\frac{1}{4}s_4(n) = \sum_{d|e=n} \frac{1}{2}s_2(d)\frac{1}{4}s_4^0(e). \tag{6.7}$$

Since the convolution of multiplicative functions is multiplicative, it follows that $s_4(n)/4$ is multiplicative. We need only evaluate this function at prime powers to obtain the formula for arbitrary positive integral n .

Lemma 25. *Let $n = p^k$ where p is prime and congruent to 1 or 3 (mod 8). Then $s_4(n)/4 = \sigma(n)$.*

Proof. Since all powers of such p are congruent to 1 or 3 (mod 8) equation (2.3) becomes

$$s_2(p^k) = 2 \left\{ \sum_{\substack{d|p^k \\ d \equiv 1 \pmod{8}}} 1 + \sum_{\substack{d|p^k \\ d \equiv 3 \pmod{8}}} 1 \right\} = 2(k+1). \tag{6.8}$$

We compute

$$\begin{aligned} 2s_4(p^k) &= \sum_{d|e=p^k} s_2(d)s_4^0(e) \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^k s_2(p^r)s_4^0(p^{k-r}) \\ &= s_2(1) \cdot s_4^0(p^k) + s_2(p) \cdot s_4^0(p^{k-1}) + \dots + s_2(p^k) \cdot s_4^0(1) \\ &= 2 \cdot 4(p-1)p^{k-1} + 2(2) \cdot 4(p-1)p^{k-2} + \dots + 2(k+1) \cdot 4 \\ &= 8((p-1)p^{k-1} + 2(p-1)p^{k-2} + \dots + k(p-1)p^0 + (k+1)). \end{aligned} \tag{6.9}$$

The last expression telescopes to $8(p^k + p^{k-1} + \dots + p^1 + 1) = 8\sigma(p^k)$. \square

Lemma 26. *Let $n = p^k$ where p is prime and congruent to 5 or 7 (mod 8). Then $s_4(n)/4 = \sigma(n)$.*

Proof. The demonstration is similar to the preceding Lemma. Note that for such p , $s_2(p^k) = 2$ if k is even or 0 if k is odd. $2 s_4(p^k)$ reduces to a telescoping sum just as in the above Lemma. \square

Lemma 27.

$$s_4(2^k) = \begin{cases} 4 & \text{if } k = 0 \\ 8 & \text{if } k = 1 \\ 24 & \text{if } k \geq 2. \end{cases} \tag{6.9}$$

Proof. Since $s_2(2^r) = 2$ for all nonnegative r by consideration of the formula for s_2 we have

$$\begin{aligned} 2 s_4(2^k) &= s_2(1) s_4^0(2^k) + s_2(2^1) s_4^0(2^{k-1}) + \dots + s_2(2^k) s_4^0(1) \\ &= 2 (s_4^0(1) + s_4^0(2) + s_4^0(2^2) + \dots) \end{aligned} \tag{6.10}$$

for $k \geq 2$. This simplifies to $s_4(2^k) = s_4^0(1) + s_4^0(2) + s_4^0(4) + 0 = 4 \cdot 1 + 2 \cdot 2 + 4 \cdot 4 = 24$ for $k \geq 2$. By truncating the above formulas we obtain $s_4(2^0) = 4$ and $s_4(2^1) = 8$. \square

Theorem 28 (Liouville).

$$s_4(2^k m) = \begin{cases} 4 \sigma(m) & \text{if } k = 0 \\ 8 \sigma(m) & \text{if } k = 1 \\ 24 \sigma(m) & \text{if } k \geq 2 \end{cases} \tag{6.10}$$

where m is odd.

Proof. Note that $s_4(n)/4$ is multiplicative. It follows that $s_4(2^k m) = s_4(2^k) \sigma(m)$ and the formula follows from the Lemma above. \square

7. Other Quadratic Forms

The representation formula for the sum of four squares can be derived by arguments similar to the above using the Hurwitz quaternions. This contrasts with the proof in [1] where the Lipschitz quaternions are used.

Since we are using maximal orders of quaternions, it is possible that representation formulas for the quadratic forms $x^2 + 2y^2 + 3z^2 + 6w^2$ and $x^2 + y^2 + 3z^2 + 3w^2$ can be proven by Bumby's technique. These forms are related to maximal orders of quaternions that are principal ideal domains. More discussion is available in [2, 3].

8. The Computation

Experimental and supporting calculations were made using GCC 3.2.2 and MAXIMA 5.9.0 on a Linux partition of a laptop computer. The computer had 256 megabytes of RAM and a pentium 4 CPU with a clock rate of 2.6 gigahertz. Some calculations were done on the Linux partition of a 133 megahertz personal computer running PUNIMAX.

9. Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank B. Haible, the maintainer of PUNIMAX, for permitting its free use for academic purposes [6].

REFERENCES

1. R. Bumby, *Sums of Four Squares*, Number Theory: New York Seminar 1991-1995 (M. Nathanson, D.V. Chudnovsky, G.V. Chudnovsky, eds.), Springer-Verlag, New York, 1996.
2. J. I. Deutsch, *A Quaternionic Proof of the Representation Formula of a Quaternary Quadratic Form*, Journal of Number Theory **113** (2005), 149–174.
3. J. I. Deutsch, *A Quaternionic Proof of the Universality of Some Quadratic Forms*, www.arxiv.org/math-NT/0406429.
4. L. E. Dickson, *History of the Theory of Numbers*, vol. III, Chelsea, New York, 1966.
5. N. Fine, *Basic Hypergeometric Series and Applications*, American Mathematical Society, Providence, Rhode Island, 1988.
6. B. Haible, *Private communication* (1997).
7. A. Hurwitz, *Vorlesungen über die Zahlentheorie der Quaternionen*, Julius Springer, Berlin, 1919.